

A STUDY ON EXAMINATION STRESS AND ACHIEVEMENT OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS STUDYING IN CUDDALORE DISTRICT

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Abstract:

The present study aims to know the high school students examination stress in relation to achievement. Simple random sampling technique has been used in the selection of the various schools in cuddalore district. To Measure Examination stress Examination stress scale by Dr. K. Saraladevi (1979) was used and for achievement score student final exam mark was considered. Result shows that there is a positive and significant correlation between examination stress and achievement.

Introduction:

General Certificate of Secondary Education suggested that the appraisal of examinations as stressful was idiosyncratic, differing from one student to another. Eight distinct but related elements of examination stress were identified, which included the anticipation of failure, poor competence beliefs and the extent to which academic credentials are valued. Examination stress was also entered, both in its subject-specific nature and in the way the experience was described by students. Academic Achievement includes the Cognitive, Affective and Psycho-motor components. But in schools, only certain aspects of the cognitive component alone are measured to indicate the Academic Achievement of the students. Even the so called Practical Examinations only test "the Knowledge of the skills and not the skills" (Pritam Singh, 1978). Thus in our schools, Academic Achievement stands only for the gains in certain aspects of the cognitive domain. Consequently, our Achievement Tests measure only this area of students' Achievement. The Affective components of learning are totally neglected in our schools.

Need and Importance of the Study:

There is growing interest in surveying students in higher education to find out how they perceive their experience and to understand the effect it has. In higher education, the autonomy and independence of the student are essential to success. Here comes the Examination Stress is conceptualized as how far the students are having a strong belief and trust on their academic side. As nowadays the higher education has been distributed by various social and technological courses the students were introduced with all brand new inventions which affects them physically and also psychologically. Above all when their Examination Stress is at their highest they will survey have a high level of academic achievement. As the investigator being teacher working in one of the higher secondary school situated in Cuddalore district, was very much interested in knowing the academic confidence and academic achievement of the high school students in his district. Hence the investigator decided to study about the academic confidence of the high school students and their academic achievement.

Objectives of the Study: To find out the relationship between examination stress and achievement of high school students.

Hypotheses of the Study: There is no significant relationship between high school students Examination Stress and Achievement.

Method of the Study: Viewing of the objectives, normative survey method was employed for the present study. The survey method is employed to find out the level of the Examination Stress and Achievement of High school students studying in High schools locating in Cuddalore District of Tamilnadu.

Tools Used: The following tool will be used for the present study. Examination stress scale by Dr. K. Saraladevi (1979)

Sampling Technique: Sampling is the process of selecting a sample from the population. The various methods of sampling techniques can be grouped under two broad heads, random sampling and non-random sampling. Random sampling technique was adopted for the present study.

Selection of Sample: The present study has been conducted in Cuddalore District of Tamilnadu. A random of sample of 300 High school students studying in high Schools were taken for the study.

Description of the Tools:

Test to Measure the Examination Stress:

Description: Though many tests are available to assess the stress of individual the investigation has chosen a standardized questionnaire of examination stress, which was constructed by Dr. K. Saraladevi (1979) for measuring examination stress of students. All the items in the questionnaire were thoroughly analysed and

formed on the basis of analyzing individuals self-concept, parental nature, study habits, emotionally and physical health. There were 65 items and out of the 65 items 50 items were negative declarative forms and 15 items were in positive form. Four point scale of always, frequently, rarely and never had been provided for each items. The subject respond to each item by a tick mark (✓) in one of the four columns provided after each statement subjects were required to respond to all items. They did not option to leave any item unanswered. Since some of the students were studying in Tamil medium questionnaire were translated into Tamil also.

Scoring of Examination Stress:

Each item in Examination Stress questionnaire was assigned a weight age from 3(Always) to 0 (Never) for favourable items. In the case of unfavourable items the range of weight age was reversed is from 0 (Always) to 3 (Never). The Examination Stress scores of the subject was the addition of all the items of scores. The theoretical range of scores was from 1 to 195 with the higher score indicating more examination stress. There was no time limit to complete 65 items. The subjects had taken approximately 45 minutes to complete all the item.

Scoring of the Tool:

Scores	Results
0	Always
1	Frequently
2	Rarely
3	Never

Establishing Reliability:

The reliability of a test may be defined as the degree of consistency with which the test measures what it does measure. A test score is called reliable when we have reason to believe it to be stable and trustworthy. The reliability of the tool was calculated using Spearman Brown’s formula for split-half method.

$$r_{11} = 2r_{hh} / 1 + r_{hh}$$

r_{11} = Reliability coefficient of the whole test.

r_{hh} = Reliability co-efficient of the half test found experimentally.

Reliability of Examination Stress:

To compute the reliability of Examination Stress, the split-half method was employed. The reliability was computed and it was found to be 0.88.

Establishing Validity:

Validity means the ability to produce finding that are in agreement with conceptual or theoretical values. It refers to the success of the scale in measuring what it is meant to measure. A test is valid, when it measures truly and accurately the ability or quality one wants to measure. Thus, validity means truthfulness of the test.

Validity of the Test on Examination Stress:

The validity of stress was found out by computing the square root of the validity co-efficient which was 0.84. Thus the examination stress was found to be highly reliable and valid for the present study.

Hypothesis:

There is no significant relationship between the high school students Examination Stress and Achievement.

Correlation Analysis:

One of the important objectives of the present study is to find out the significance of relationship between the Examination Stress and Achievement of the high school students. For this, the investigator calculated the co-efficient of correlation (γ).

Co-efficient of Correlation of Examination Stress and Achievement of High School Students:

Variables	‘ γ ’ Value
Examination Stress	0.031*
Achievement	

* Not significant

The computed co-efficient correlation ‘ γ ’ value 0.031 denotes that there is no relationship between the high school students Examination Stress and Achievement. Hence, the hypothesis is accepted.

Recommendations:

The results of the study shows that the high school students Examination Stress and Achievement level is very high.

- The student should be helped in realizing his strength and weakness. For this we should arrange for the guidance and counseling services in our schools for helping students in making confidence with their problems.
- Students physical and adjustment and his social, emotional and aesthetic development should be properly attended to. There should be perfect harmony and balance between the different aspect of

growth and development. Hence the curriculum should includes social activities such as N.S.S. Scout, cultural programmes and so on

- The teacher, when he acts as strict disciplinarian prevents a genuinely friendly atmosphere in the class room. The teacher must provide opportunities and give necessary assistance to the child for the satisfaction of basic needs.
- In schools job oriented courses should be started. Educational institutions may be attached to industries so as to enable the students to fit in the society immediately after their studies. This will be immensely helpful for the vocational students.
- The parents and teachers should themselves try to practice the right ways and good habits to help children in adjusting with society and culture. The parent teachers association must functioning well in all the schools.
- Dynamic methods such as seminar, symposia, brain storming should be followed by the teachers in teaching the students.

Effective study habits can be inculcated to prevent examination stress. Development of creative thinking of new solutions in tackling

Conclusion:

From the analysis of the data collected from the choosen sample of students, it is evident that, the high school students level of Examination is very high and their level of Achievement is high. Further, there is positive relationship between the students Examination Stress and Achievement.

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